

Action of Amines on Quinolinic Acid.

BY ANANDA KISHORE DAS AND INDU BHUSON SARKER.

The action of mono- and diamines on phthalic acid has been studied by several investigators. A study of similar reactions on quinolinic acid was expected to be of interest.

Ghosh (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 1105) in an attempt to prepare compounds like phthaleins from quinolinic acid noticed that with aniline it gave quinanils similar to phthalanils. Sen-Gupta and Sarkar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 401) studied the action of benzidine and tolidine on it, while Sircar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 145) also studied in detail the action of phenylhydrazine.

Philips (*Ber.*, 1894, 27, 839) studied the action of ammonia on quinolinic acid. It was thought desirable to follow the course of the reaction of this compound with mono- and diamines. In this paper, its action on aniline has been studied under different experimental conditions.

When aniline is mixed with quinolinic acid the mixture gets warm and aniline quinolinate (mono) is formed, a possibility foreshadowed by Meyer (*Ber.*, 1899, 32, 2122). On keeping this compound just near its melting point for a few minutes it changes to diquinolinate. Either of the above or a mixture of aniline and quinolinic acid on heating with glacial acetic acid gives the dianilide which when heated at 225-240° changes to quinanil (Ghosh, *loc. cit.*, records m.p. 248-251°; Engler, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 1789, gives 228°). The quinanil on boiling with alcoholic ammonia changes to quinanilic acid, m. p. 217° and this changes back to the anil on heating.

The fact that the quinolates respond to diazo test and regenerate aniline on treatment with cold dilute caustic soda proves that they are additive compounds, which is also confirmed by analysis.

The quinanil obtained by Engler, Ghosh and by the present authors differs widely in its melting point, and while the compound obtained by Ghosh's method could not be hydrolysed by boiling

alcoholic potash or strong hydrochloric acid, that obtained by us could easily be hydrolysed by either of these reagents.

A study of literature of the corresponding compounds of phthalic acid reveals a similar divergence in the melting points. Thus phthalanilic acid has been found to have a melting point of 158° (Zincke, *Annalen*, 1884, 225, 375), 170° (Meyer, *loc. cit.*), 192° (Laurent, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1847, 48, 605). Phthalaldianilide has m. p. of 251° (Meulen, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1897, 15, 345) and 231° (Rogoff, *Ber.*, 1897, 30, 1442).

An attempt was, therefore, made to isolate some of these compounds to get a clue to this peculiar divergence in their melting points. It has been found that while Meyer's compound is the real phthalanilic acid, that of Zincke is a phthalate with one molecule of aniline, the additive nature of the compound is determined as with the corresponding compounds of quinolinic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Aniline quinolinate (mono).—Quinolinic acid (0.5 g.) and excess of aniline when mixed in a test tube got warm and soon changed to a solid mass. After leaving overnight, the solid was crystallised from alcohol as colourless prisms, m. p. 137° (decomp.). It solidifies at about $160-65^{\circ}$ and remelts at 187° . It is highly soluble in alcohol and acetic acid. It also dissolves readily in a solution of sodium carbonate with effervescence and in cold caustic soda with separation of aniline. It responds to diazo test. (Found: N, 11.1; aniline, 36.1. $C_{13}H_{12}N_2O_4$ requires N, 10.8; aniline, 35.8 per cent).

Aniline quinolinate (di).—The above substance (0.5 g.) was heated in a test tube gradually up to its melting point and the temperature raised slowly up to about 160° . The solid is crystallised from alcohol as colourless needles, m. p. 187° (decomp.). It is soluble in alcohol and acetic acid and also dissolves in caustic alkalis in the cold with separation of aniline. It can be diazotised with cold dilute HCl and coupled with β -naphthol. (Found: aniline, 52.0. $C_{19}H_{19}N_3O_4$ requires aniline, 52.0 per cent).

Quinolinyl dianilide.—A mixture of quinolinic acid (1 part) and aniline (2 parts) and a few drops of glacial acetic acid was heated on a water-bath for about 3 hours. The mixture at first melted and then solidified. The solid was collected and crystallised from alcohol in long colourless needles melting at 225° . It is soluble in boiling

alcohol and insoluble in cold alkalis and can be hydrolysed with strong hydrochloric acid. (Found: N, 13·5; aniline, 59·0. $C_{19}H_{15}N_3O_2$ requires N, 13·25; aniline, 58·7 per cent).

(a) Quinolinic acid (0·5 g.) was mixed with excess of acetanilide and heated at 125° for 2 hours. On cooling the solid was crystallised from alcohol as fine colourless needles, m. p. 225°.

(b) Aniline quinolinate (mono) was heated above 187° for 3 hours. When frothing was over the product was crystallised from alcohol as colourless needles, m. p. 225°.

(c) Aniline quinolinate (di-) was kept above its melting point for about an hour. The solid when crystallised melted at 225°.

Quinanil.—Quinolinyldianilide (0·5 g.) was heated at 225-240° for 1 hour and the solid crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 208°. It is soluble in alcohol and acetic acid but insoluble in cold caustic soda. (Found: N, 12·8; aniline, 40·8. $C_{13}H_8N_2O_2$ requires N, 12·5; aniline, 41·5 per cent).

Quinanilic acid.—Quinanil (0·5 g.) was heated with alcoholic ammonia for an hour under reflux. The solid separating was filtered, acidified with acetic acid, washed and crystallised from hot alcohol in colourless laminæ, m. p. 217° (decomp.). It is soluble in alcohol and in sodium carbonate solution with effervescence. If kept at the temperature of decomposition for about 15 minutes it changes to quinanil melting at 208°. (Found: N, 12·2; aniline, 39·0. $C_{13}H_{10}N_2O_3$ requires N, 11·5; aniline, 38·4 per cent).

Aniline phthalate (mono).—Phthalic acid (1 g.) was mixed with excess of aniline. The mixture which got warm and soon solidified was left overnight. The solid was crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 158° (decomp.). It is soluble in alcohol and acetic acid and dissolves in cold sodium carbonate solution with the separation of aniline. It responds to diazo test. (Found: aniline, 35·9. $C_{14}H_{13}O_4N$ requires aniline, 36·0 per cent).

Phthalic acid (1 g.) and excess of aniline was heated in a toluene bath for 1 hour. The solid that separated on cooling crystallised from alcohol in needles, m. p. 158°.

Phthalanil.—The above substance was kept at a temperature of 160-65° for an hour and the solid crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 205°. (Laurent gives the m. p. 203-05°).

Phthalanilic acid.—Phthalanil (1 g.) was heated with alcoholic potash for 15 minutes. The solid that separated on cooling was washed with dilute acetic acid and then crystallised from alcohol in

colourless needles, m. p. 170°. (Meyer, 170°; Zincke, 158°; Laurent, 190°).

This substance cannot be diazotised with cold dilute hydrochloric acid as the one melting at 158°, but can be diazotised after boiling with strong hydrochloric acid. When heated above its m. p. it is converted readily into phthalanil.

The percentage of nitrogen in anils, anilides and quinolines being very close it was thought desirable to confirm the results by estimating volumetrically the aniline content, where the divergence of percentage is greater, in the different types of compounds by the Maurice Franchois method (*J. Phar.*, 1899, *vi*, 9, 521) which was found to work very satisfactorily.

Further work is in progress. We take this opportunity of thanking the Principal of the college for his kind interest in the work.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
COTTON COLLEGE,
GAUHATI (ASSAM).

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